

On Designing efficient and optimized deep convolutional neural networks: A Review

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1. Introduction

With success of Deep CNN networks for computer vision problems, there has been a tremendous progress in designing efficient and optimized networks. However, developing Deep CNN networks, often requires significant architecture engineering efforts, empirical evaluation and hyper parameter exploration.

The main objective of this talk is to serve as a guide for selecting a deep CNN image classification networks often used a backbone network for feature extraction, in many computer vision problems. To this end, we cover broad topics on network microarchitectures. & microarchitectures choices, architectures hyper parameters, training hyper parameters, and best usage for end application.

We evaluate the different trade-offs between accuracy and speed, number of operations measured by multiply-adds (Madd), number of parameters, inference time and preferred choice for mobile devices. Finally, we propose several promising directions and tasks, to serve as guidelines for future work.

2. Aim

To explore large architectural sub space for Deep CNN networks and proposal for new directions.

3. Material and methods

To be described in detail during the talk

4. Results

To be described in detail during the talk

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5. Conclusions

We provide a comprehensive survey of the main aspects of designing efficient and optimized Deep CNN image classification networks. We have also identified common architectural choices across different networks. And we also demonstrate that how we can build new and better architectures, from ideas taken from this study. We hope that this will help the practitioner choose the right network specific to their end application.

6. Keywords

Deep CNN image classification network, VGG, Resnet, Inception, SphereNet, Xception, NasNet, Mobilenet, Densenet, ShuffleNet, Mobile Facenet, Highway network and Condense Net.

Author biography

Jalaj Jain is an applied researcher, in Machine Vision and video processing. His research interests span a range of avenues in Computer Vision and machine learning. The most prominent one is image quality enhancement (Noise reduction and super resolution), face recognition, video summarization, one shot learning, memory networks, weak semi supervised learning and object tracking. Jalaj have been selected as an Exceptional talent nomination in Machine/Deep Learning by UK Tech city, in year 2018. More recently, he has been selected as a MIT Technology Review Global Panel (A Global community of thought leaders). Jalaj is also an active volunteer with united nations London, UK and British Heart Foundations, London UK.

Jalaj is currently working as a new R&D Group with a Aframe, a privately own company based in London UK. Jalaj has previously worked with Sanyo Digital signal processing research lab, Kumagaya Japan & Bangalore, India and Samsung visual display, Suwon, South Korea. Jalaj was also instrumental in setting and growing the USA based technology startup, Metta technology during year 2005-2008, in India.